

QUIZ**LAST NAME: FAYE****FIRST NAME: Abdoulaye****PROGRAM CODE: MBASD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Laurent Cleenewerck**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Mac

QUIZ: A JOURNEY IN STYLE

1. **In which condition it is necessitated to use citation?¹**

- When quoting exact texts from a source.**
- When you utilize any information or technique that are owing to others.**
- When you recount a major event in U.S. History such as the assassination of Abraham Lincoln.
- When rewording concepts that are related to a particular source regardless if you quote exact words from it.**

2. **When do you use the bar chart as most effective way to present results?²**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 51–52.

² Turabian, 65–66.

- To determine relationships between two different factors.
 - To reveal compared values that can be seen at a glance between different groups.**
 - To reveal changes of pattern over short or long periods of time.
 - To compare parts of a whole.
3. **By convention, which types of source can be omitted from a bibliography?³**
- well-known reference works, such as major dictionaries and encyclopedias.**
 - the Bible and other sacred works.**
 - Citations of legal cases generally take the same form for courts at all levels.**
 - abstract documents in published manuscript collections.
4. **According to Turabian, which type of citation styles are used to cite?⁴**

³ Turabian, 95.

⁴ Turabian, 87–88.

- Bibliography style.**
 - Footnote style.
 - Author-Date style.**
 - Endnote style.
5. **According to Turabian, which type of Bibliography style can be used?⁵**
- Selected bibliography which do not include all works cited in notes.**
 - Single-author bibliography uses a standard bibliography and additionally comprises separate lists of sources produced by one author or group of authors.**
 - End note bibliography where all biographies are listed at the end of the papers using in-text code.
 - Annotated bibliography is where some researchers note each bibliography entry with a brief description of the work's contents or relevance to their research**
6. **What are the different ways of formatting parenthetical notes?⁶**
- 'Page numbers only' when it is possible to identify the specific text from the text.**
 - 'Author and Title' when the result of the finding can apply at any given time.
 - 'Author and page' number if author cannot be identified from reading the cited text.**

⁵ Turabian, 93.

⁶ Turabian, 99.

- 'Title and page number' when author can be identified in the text.
7. **When capitalizing headlines, which part should be excepted?**⁷
- Do not capitalise articles (a, an, the).
- Do not capitalise classical and medieval works names cited.
- Do not capitalise the second part of a species name.
- Do not capitalise prepositions (of, in, at, above, under, and so forth).
8. **According to the EU Style Guide, which form of address should be used in a letter to a European Union Commissioner?**⁸
- Ms X, Vice-President.
- Mr Y, Member of the Commission responsible for
- Ms Z (Member of the Commission).
- Mr Commissioner A.
9. **8. According to the EU Style Guide, foreign word and phrases used in English Text should...**⁹
- Have the appropriate accent.
- Be highlighted.
- Be italicised.

⁷ Turabian, 185.

⁸ Directorate-General for Translation, *European Commission English Style Guide*, 2011, 62.

⁹ Directorate-General for Translation, 31.

Be underlined.

10. **According to the Euclid University's Coursepack which of the following are accepted for paraphrasing.¹⁰**

Must be using your words.

Must be accurate translation of the author's ideas.

Your writing style must be exactly the same as the author has used.

When perfectly paraphrasing the renowned author there is no need to cite the source.

REFERENCE LIST

Directorate-General for Translation. *European Commission English Style Guide*, 2011.

Euclid University. 'ACA-401 Coursepack-PERIOD 1'. Euclid University, 2015.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Euclid University, 'ACA-401 Coursepack-PERIOD 1' (Euclid University, 2015), 24,
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.